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Evaluation of conservation status of reported Indian Odonates (Insecta: Odonata)

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Abstract- This study assesses the conservation status of all dragonflies and damselflies reported from India. 3 suborders, 17 families and 504 species of odonates are reported from India till now. IUCN has done excellent work on assessing status of conservation, population trends, and distribution of odonates. IUCN Red List provides a comprehensive catalogue and framework for evaluating the conservation status of odonates. However no consolidated and annotated list of Indian odonates with their conservation status is present, so this study fills this research gap and provides a complete list of reported Indian odonates along with their conservation status. Maximum odonate species were reported under Least Concern and Data Deficient Categories.

Keywords: IUCN Red List, Odonata, DD, LC, NE, NT, VU, EN, CR, CITES

INTRODUCTION

Odonates are cosmopolitan, aquatic, carnivorous, diurnal, primitive group of flying insects. Being predator and prey, both in larval and adult stage, they play a significant role in the food web in freshwater ecosystem. Study of odonates is called Odonatology, which is a branch of Entomology. It includes three orders viz. Anisoptera, Anisozygoptera and Zygoptera.^{1,2} There are total 6453 species of odonates are reported globally. In India total 504 species under 157 genera and 17 families of odonates are reported with exclusion of 23 subspecies, out of which 175 odonate species are reported endemic to India.^{3,4} IUCN (International Union of Conservation of Nature) was founded in 1964, since then it is working on conservation of plants, fungi and animals. It accumulates and provides critical data for conservation, monitoring and policy making. IUCN Red List also known as Red Data Book

and Red List of Threatened Species provides the world's most comprehensive catalogue of the conservation status of biological species. IUCN Red List is prepared scientifically on basis of following five criteria system. viz. **Criterion A:** population size reductions, which evaluates suspected population size reductions over the longer of 10 years or three generations; **Criterion B:** Geographic Range, which assesses species with small geographic ranges that are experiencing continuing decline or extreme fluctuations; **Criterion C:** Small Population Size and Decline, which applies to species with small populations that are experiencing continuing decline; **Criterion D:** Very Small or Restricted Population, which addresses species with very small populations or very restricted areas of occupancy; **Criterion E:** Quantitative Analysis, which involves formal population viability analysis or other quantitative methods to estimate extinction probability; The IUCN Red List classifies species into nine categories based on their extinction risk.

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viz. Extinct (EX), Extinct in the Wild (EW), Critically Endangered (CR), Endangered (EN), Vulnerable (VU), Near Threatened (NT), Least Concern (LC), Data Deficient (DD) and Not Evaluated (NE).⁵

Table 1. List of Indian Odonate Species with their Conservation Status

MATERIALS & METHODS

Comprehensive checklist of Indian Odonates is parsimony examined using Red Data Book to assess conservation status of each species.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

India has 7.81 % biodiversity of world. The Himalayan Relict Dragonfly (*Epiophlebia laidlawi*) is listed under Schedule-1 Part-J of Wildlife Protection Act (2022). Odonates are not listed under any appendices of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora). No odonate species are reported to be invasive in India. *Sympetrum dilatatum* (Family Libellulidae) is the only extinct odonate species of world. In India all 3 suborders (Anisoptera, Anisozygoptera and Zygoptera) of odonates are reported. 17 families of odonata were reported from India, out of which 7 families (Aeshnidae, Chlorogomphidae, Cordulegasteridae, Cordulidae, Gomphidae, Libellulidae and Macromiidae,) belonged to Suborder Anisoptera, while 9 families (Calopterygidae, Chlorocyphidae, Coenagrionidae, Euphaeidae, Lestidae, Philogangidae, Platynecmididae, Platystictidae and Synlestidae) belonged to suborder Zygoptera. Only single family (Epiophlebiidae) with single species (*Epiophlebia laidlawi*) belonged to suborder Anisozygoptera reported from India. We provide a complete annotated list of 504 Indian odonate species with their conservation status listed against them (Table 1). Out of 504 Indian odonate species, no species was reported in EX and EW category. Only single species *Protosticta myristicaensis* (Family Platystictidae) was reported under CR. Three species viz. *Orthetrum andamanicum* (Family Libellulidae), *Idionyx galeata* (Family Macromiidae) and *Libellago balus* (Family Chlorocyphidae) were reported under EN. 31 Indian odonate species are not evaluated for their conservation status (Table 2 and Graph 1).

Species		Conservation Status	
Suborder Anisoptera	Family Aeshnidae	<i>Aeshna juncea</i>	LC
		<i>Aeshna mixta</i>	LC
		<i>Aeshna petalura</i>	LC
		<i>Anaciaeschna jaspidea</i>	LC
		<i>Anaciaeschna martini</i>	LC
		<i>Anax ephippiger</i>	LC
		<i>Anax guttatus</i>	LC
		<i>Anax immaculifrons</i>	LC
		<i>Anax imperator</i>	LC
		<i>Anax indicus</i>	LC
		<i>Anax nigrofasciatus</i>	LC
		<i>Anax panybeus</i>	LC
		<i>Anax parthenope</i>	LC
		<i>Cephalaeschna acanthifrons</i>	DD
		<i>Cephalaeschna acutifrons</i>	DD
		<i>Cephalaeschna klapperichi</i>	DD
		<i>Cephalaeschna masoni</i>	DD
		<i>Cephalaeschna orbifrons</i>	LC
		<i>Cephalaeschna patrai</i>	NE
		<i>Cephalaeschna triadica</i>	DD
		<i>Cephalaeschna viridifrons</i>	LC
		<i>Gynacantha albistyla</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha andamanae</i>	NE
		<i>Gynacantha anandmati</i>	NE
		<i>Gynacantha arnaudi</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha bainbriggei</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha bayadera</i>	LC
		<i>Gynacantha biharica</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha dravida</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha khasiaca</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha millardi</i>	LC
	<i>Gynacantha odoneli</i>	DD	
	<i>Gynacantha pallampurica</i>	DD	
	<i>Gynacantha rammohani</i>	DD	
	<i>Gynacantha rotundata</i>	DD	
	<i>Gynacantha subinterrupta</i>	LC	
	<i>Gynacanthaeschna sikkima</i>	LC	
	<i>Oligoaeschna andamani</i>	DD	
	<i>Periaeschna flinti</i>	LC	
	<i>Periaeschna magdalena</i>	LC	
	<i>Periaeschna nocturnalis</i>	LC	
	<i>Periaeschna unifasciata</i>	DD	
	<i>Petaliaeschna fletcheri</i>	DD	
	<i>Planaeschna intercedens</i>	NT	
	<i>Planaeschna poumai</i>	NE	
	<i>Polycanthagyna erythromelas</i>	LC	
	<i>Polycanthagyna ornithocephala</i>	LC	
	<i>Sarasaeschna decorata</i>	DD	
	<i>Sarasaeschna khasiana</i>	DD	
	<i>Sarasaeschna martini</i>	DD	
	<i>Sarasaeschna speciosa</i>	DD	
	<i>Tetracanthagyna waterhousei</i>	LC	
	Family Chlorogomphidae	<i>Chlorogomphus campioni</i>	LC
		<i>Chlorogomphus fraseri</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus mortoni</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus preciosus</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus schmidti</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus xanthoptera</i>	V
		<i>Chloropetalia selysi</i>	V
		<i>Watanabeopetalia atkinsoni</i>	LC
	Family Cordulegasteridae	<i>Anotogaster basilis</i>	NE
		<i>Anotogaster gregoryi</i>	LC
		<i>Gynacantha rotundata</i>	DD
		<i>Gynacantha subinterrupta</i>	LC

Rawal Deepak- Evaluation of conservation status of reported Indian Odonates (Insecta: Odonata)

		<i>Gynacanthaeschna sikkima</i>	LC
		<i>Oligoaeschna andamani</i>	DD
		<i>Periaeschna flinti</i>	LC
		<i>Periaeschna magdalena</i>	LC
		<i>Periaeschna nocturnalis</i>	LC
		<i>Periaeschna unifasciata</i>	DD
		<i>Petaliaeschna fletcheri</i>	DD
		<i>Planaeschna intersedens</i>	NT
		<i>Planaeschna poumai</i>	NE
		<i>Polycanthagyna erythromelas</i>	LC
		<i>Polycanthagyna ornithocephala</i>	LC
		<i>Sarasaeschna decorata</i>	DD
		<i>Sarasaeschna khasiana</i>	DD
		<i>Sarasaeschna martini</i>	DD
		<i>Sarasaeschna speciosa</i>	DD
		<i>Tetracanthagyna waterhousei</i>	LC
	Family Chlorogomphidae	<i>Chlorogomphus campioni</i>	LC
		<i>Chlorogomphus fraseri</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus mortoni</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus preciosus</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus schmidti</i>	DD
		<i>Chlorogomphus xanthoptera</i>	V
		<i>Chloropetalia selysi</i>	V
		<i>Watanabeopetalia atkinsoni</i>	LC
	Family Cordulegasteridae	<i>Anotogaster basilis</i>	NE
		<i>Anotogaster gregoryi</i>	LC
		<i>Anotogaster nipalensis</i>	LC
		<i>Cordulegaster brevistigma</i>	LC
		<i>Cordulegaster parvistigma</i>	DD
		<i>Neallogaster hermoniae</i>	LC
		<i>Neallogaster latifrons</i>	LC
		<i>Neallogaster ornata</i>	NT
		<i>Neallogaster schmidti</i>	DD
	Family Corduliidae	<i>Hemicordulia asiatica</i>	LC
		<i>Somatochlora daviesi</i>	DD
	Family Gomphidae	<i>Acrogomphus fraseri</i>	DD
		<i>Anisogomphus bivittatus</i>	LC
		<i>Anisogomphus caudalis</i>	DD
		<i>Anisogomphus occipitalis</i>	LC
		<i>Anisogomphus orites</i>	DD
		<i>Anormogomphus heteropterus</i>	LC
		<i>Anormogomphus kiritschenkoi</i>	NT
		<i>Asiagomphus nilgircus</i>	DD
		<i>Asiagomphus odoneli</i>	DD
		<i>Asiagomphus personatus</i>	NT
		<i>Burmagomphus cauvericus</i>	DD
		<i>Burmagomphus chaukulensis</i>	NE
		<i>Burmagomphus divaricatus</i>	LC
		<i>Burmagomphus hasimanicus</i>	DD
		<i>Burmagomphus laidlawi</i>	DD
		<i>Burmagomphus pyramidalis</i>	LC
		<i>Burmagomphus sivalikensis</i>	LC
		<i>Cyclogomphus flavoannulatus</i>	DD
		<i>Cyclogomphus heterostylus</i>	DD
		<i>Cyclogomphus wilkinsi</i>	DD
		<i>Cyclogomphus ypsilon</i>	V
		<i>Davidioides martini</i>	DD
		<i>Davidius aberrans</i>	LC
		<i>Davidius davidii</i>	LC
		<i>Davidius delineatus</i>	NE
		<i>Davidius kumaonensis</i>	DD
		<i>Davidius malloryi</i>	DD
		<i>Dubito gomphus bidentatus</i>	DD

		<i>Euthygomphus martini</i>	NE
		<i>Gomphidia fletcheri</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia ganeshi</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia kodaguensis</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia leonorae</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia platyceps</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia podhigai</i>	DD
		<i>Gomphidia t-nigrum</i>	LC
		<i>Gomphidia williamsoni</i>	DD
		<i>Heliogomphus kalarensis</i>	DD
		<i>Heliogomphus promelas</i>	NT
		<i>Heliogomphus selysi</i>	LC
		<i>Heliogomphus spirillus</i>	DD
		<i>Ictinogomphus angulosus</i>	LC
		<i>Ictinogomphus decoratus</i>	LC
		<i>Ictinogomphus distinctus</i>	DD
		<i>Ictinogomphus kishori</i>	DD
		<i>Ictinogomphus pertinax</i>	LC
		<i>Ictinogomphus rapax</i>	LC
		<i>Lamelligomphus biforceps</i>	LC
		<i>Lamelligomphus nilgiriensis</i>	NE
		<i>Lamelligomphus risi</i>	DD
		<i>Macrogomphus annulatus</i>	DD
		<i>Macrogomphus montanus</i>	DD
		<i>Macrogomphus robustus</i>	DD
		<i>Macrogomphus seductus</i>	DD
		<i>Macrogomphus wynaadicus</i>	DD
		<i>Megalogomphus bicornutus</i>	DD
		<i>Megalogomphus flavicolor</i>	DD
		<i>Megalogomphus hannyingtoni</i>	NT
		<i>Megalogomphus smithii</i>	DD
		<i>Megalogomphus superbus</i>	DD
		<i>Melligomphus acinaces</i>	DD
		<i>Merogomphus longistigma</i>	DD
		<i>Merogomphus tamaracherriensis</i>	NE
		<i>Microgomphus souteri</i>	LC
		<i>Microgomphus torquatus</i>	DD
		<i>Microgomphus verticalis</i>	DD
		<i>Nepogomphus modestus</i>	LC
		<i>Nepogomphus walli</i>	LC
		<i>Nihonogomphus pulcherrimus</i>	DD
		<i>Nychogomphus duaricus</i>	LC
		<i>Nychogomphus saundersii</i>	NE
		<i>Nychogomphus striatus</i>	DD
		<i>Onychogomphus cacharicus</i>	DD
		<i>Onychogomphus cerastis</i>	DD
		<i>Onychogomphus grammicus</i>	DD
		<i>Onychogomphus malabarensis</i>	DD
		<i>Onychogomphus meghalayanus</i>	DD
		<i>Ophiogomphus reductus</i>	LC
		<i>Orientogomphus indicus</i>	DD
		<i>Paragomphus echinoccipitalis</i>	DD
		<i>Paragomphus lindgreni</i>	DD
		<i>Paragomphus lineatus</i>	LC
		<i>Perissogomphus stevensi</i>	LC
		<i>Phaenandrogomphus aureus</i>	DD
		<i>Platygomphus benritarum</i>	NE
		<i>Platygomphus dolabratus</i>	LC
		<i>Scalmogomphus bistrigatus</i>	LC
		<i>Scalmogomphus schmidti</i>	NE
		<i>Stylogomphus inglisi</i>	LC
	Family Libellulidae	<i>Acisoma panorpoides</i>	LC
		<i>Aethriamanta brevipennis</i>	LC
		<i>Agrioptera insignis</i>	LC
		<i>Amphithemis vacillans</i>	DD

Biospectra : Vol. 20(1), March, 2025

An International Biannual Refereed Journal of Life Sciences

	<i>Atratothemis reelsi</i>	DD
	<i>Brachydiplax chalybea</i>	LC
	<i>Brachydiplax farinosa</i>	LC
	<i>Brachydiplax sobrina</i>	LC
	<i>Brachythemis contaminata</i>	LC
	<i>Bradinopyga geminata</i>	LC
	<i>Bradinopyga konkanensis</i>	NE
	<i>Camacinia gigantea</i>	LC
	<i>Camacinia harterti</i>	DD
	<i>Cratilla lineata</i>	LC
	<i>Cratilla metallica</i>	LC
	<i>Crocothemis erythraea</i>	LC
	<i>Crocothemis servilia</i>	LC
	<i>Diplacodes lefebvrei</i>	LC
	<i>Diplacodes nebulosa</i>	LC
	<i>Diplacodes trivialis</i>	LC
	<i>Epithemis mariae</i>	LC
	<i>Epithemis wayanadensis</i>	NE
	<i>Hydrobasileus croceus</i>	LC
	<i>Hylaeothemis apicalis</i>	DD
	<i>Hylaeothemis gardeneri</i>	DD
	<i>Indothemis carnatica</i>	LC
	<i>Indothemis limbata</i>	LC
	<i>Lathrecista asiatica</i>	LC
	<i>Libellula quadrimaculata</i>	LC
	<i>Lyriothemis acigastrea</i>	DD
	<i>Lyriothemis bivittata</i>	LC
	<i>Lyriothemis cleis</i>	LC
	<i>Lyriothemis flava</i>	LC
	<i>Lyriothemis mortoni</i>	DD
	<i>Macrodiplex cora</i>	LC
	<i>Nannophya pygmaea</i>	LC
	<i>Nannophyopsis clara</i>	LC
	<i>Nesoxenia lineata</i>	LC
	<i>Neurothemis degener</i>	NE
	<i>Neurothemis fluctuans</i>	LC
	<i>Neurothemis fulvia</i>	LC
	<i>Neurothemis intermedia</i>	LC
	<i>Neurothemis ramburi</i>	LC
	<i>Neurothemis tullia</i>	LC
	<i>Onychothemis testacea</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum andamanicum</i>	E
	<i>Orthetrum brunneum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum cancellatum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum chrysis</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum coerulescens</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum erythronigrum</i>	NE
	<i>Orthetrum glaucum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum internum</i>	NE
	<i>Orthetrum luzonicum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum martensi</i>	DD
	<i>Orthetrum pruinatum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum sabina</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum taeniolatum</i>	LC
	<i>Orthetrum testaceum</i>	NE
	<i>Orthetrum triangulare</i>	LC
	<i>Palpopleura sexmaculata</i>	LC
	<i>Pantala flavescens</i>	LC
	<i>Phyllothemis eltoni</i>	DD
	<i>Potamarcha congener</i>	LC
	<i>Pseudothemis zonata</i>	LC
	<i>Pseudotranea prateri</i>	DD
	<i>Rhodothemis rufa</i>	LC
	<i>Rhyothemis phyllis</i>	LC
	<i>Rhyothemis plutonia</i>	LC
	<i>Rhyothemis triangularis</i>	LC

		<i>Rhyothemis variegata</i>	LC
		<i>Selysiothemis nigra</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum arenicolor</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum fonscolombii</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum haritonovi</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum hypomelas</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum meridionale</i>	LC
		<i>Sympetrum orientale</i>	DD
		<i>Sympetrum speciosum</i>	NE
		<i>Sympetrum striolatum</i>	LC
		<i>Tetrathemis platyptera</i>	LC
		<i>Tholymis tillarga</i>	LC
		<i>Tramea basilari</i>	LC
		<i>Tramea eurybia</i>	LC
		<i>Tramea limbata</i>	LC
		<i>Tramea transmarina</i>	LC
		<i>Tramea virginia</i>	LC
		<i>Trithemis aurora</i>	LC
		<i>Trithemis festiva</i>	LC
		<i>Trithemis kirbyi</i>	LC
		<i>Trithemis pallidinervis</i>	LC
		<i>Urothemis signata</i>	LC
		<i>Zygonyx iris</i>	LC
		<i>Zygonyx torridus</i>	LC
		<i>Zyxomma obtusum</i>	LC
		<i>Zyxomma breviventre</i>	DD
		<i>Zyxomma petiolatum</i>	LC
	Family Macromiidae	<i>Epophthalmia frontalis</i>	LC
		<i>Epophthalmia vittata</i>	LC
		<i>Epophthalmia vittigera</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia annaimallaiensis</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia bellicosa</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia cingulata</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia cupricincta</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia ellisoni</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia flavicincta</i>	DD
		<i>Macromia flavocolorata</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia flavovittata</i>	DD
		<i>Macromia ida</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia indica</i>	DD
		<i>Macromia irata</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia moorei</i>	LC
		<i>Macromia pallida</i>	DD
		<i>Macromia whitei</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx corona</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx galeata</i>	E
		<i>Idionyx gomantakensis</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx imbricata</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx intricata</i>	LC
		<i>Idionyx minima</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx nadganiensis</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx nilgiriensis</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx optata</i>	NT
		<i>Idionyx periyashola</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx rhinocerosides</i>	LC
		<i>Idionyx saffronata</i>	DD
		<i>Idionyx stevensi</i>	LC
		<i>Idionyx travancorensis</i>	DD
		<i>Macromidia donaldi</i>	LC
Suborder Anisozygoptera	Family Epiophlebiidae	<i>Epiophlebia laidlawi</i>	NT
Suborder Zygoptera	Family Calopterygidae	<i>Caliphaea confusa</i>	LC
		<i>Echo margarita</i>	LC
		<i>Echo perornata</i>	DD
		<i>Matrona nigripectus</i>	LC

Rawal Deepak- Evaluation of conservation status of reported Indian Odonates (Insecta: Odonata)

		<i>Neurobasis chinensis</i>	LC
		<i>Vestalaria smaragdina</i>	LC
		<i>Vestalis apicalis</i>	LC
		<i>Vestalis gracilis</i>	LC
		<i>Vestalis submontana</i>	LC
	Family Chlorocyphidae	<i>Aristocypha cuneata</i>	DD
		<i>Aristocypha fenestrella</i>	LC
		<i>Aristocypha hilaryae</i>	DD
		<i>Aristocypha immaculata</i>	LC
		<i>Aristocypha quadrimaculata</i>	LC
		<i>Aristocypha spuria</i>	LC
		<i>Aristocypha trifasciata</i>	LC
		<i>Calocypha laidlawi</i>	DD
		<i>Heliocypha biforata</i>	LC
		<i>Heliocypha bisignata</i>	LC
		<i>Heliocypha perforata</i>	LC
		<i>Heterocypha vitrinella</i>	DD
		<i>Indocypha vittata</i>	NT
		<i>Libellago andamanensis</i>	V
		<i>Libellago aurantiaca</i>	LC
		<i>Libellago balus</i>	E
		<i>Libellago blanda</i>	V
		<i>Libellago indica</i>	LC
		<i>Libellago lineata</i>	LC
		<i>Paracypha unimaculata</i>	LC
		<i>Rhinocypha ignipennis</i>	LC
		<i>Rhinocypha trimaculata</i>	DD
	Family Coenagrionidae	<i>Aciagrion approximans</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion azureum</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion borneense</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion hisopa</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion occidentale</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion olympicum</i>	LC
		<i>Aciagrion pallidum</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis clauseni</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis corbeti</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis dabreui</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis femina</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis kalinga</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis keralensis</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis lacteola</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis nana</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis pieris</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i>	LC
		<i>Agriocnemis splendidissima</i>	LC
		<i>Amphiallagma parvum</i>	LC
		<i>Archibasis oscillans</i>	LC
		<i>Argiocnemis rubescens</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion aeruginosum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion auranticum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion azureum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion calamineum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion cerinorubellum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion chromothorax</i>	DD
		<i>Ceriagrion coromandelianum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion fallax</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion olivaceum</i>	LC
		<i>Ceriagrion pratermissum</i>	NE
		<i>Ceriagrion rubiae</i>	LC
		<i>Coenagrion exclamationis</i>	DD
		<i>Enallagma cyathigerum</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura forcipata</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura inarmata</i>	DD
		<i>Ischnura nursei</i>	LC

		<i>Ischnura pumilio</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura rubilio</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura rufostigma</i>	LC
		<i>Ischnura senegalensis</i>	LC
		<i>Mortonagrion aborense</i>	LC
		<i>Mortonagrion varralli</i>	DD
		<i>Paracercion calamorum</i>	LC
		<i>Paracercion malayanum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion andamanicum</i>	DD
		<i>Pseudagrion australasiae</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion bidentatum</i>	DD
		<i>Pseudagrion decorum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion hypermelas</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion indicum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion laidlawi</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion malabaricum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion microcephalum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion pilidorsum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion pruinsum</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion rubriceps</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion spencei</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudagrion williamsoni</i>	LC
	Family Euphaeidae	<i>Anisopleura comes</i>	LC
		<i>Anisopleura lestoides</i>	LC
		<i>Anisopleura subplatystyla</i>	LC
		<i>Anisopleura vallei</i>	V
		<i>Bayadera hyalina</i>	LC
		<i>Bayadera indica</i>	LC
		<i>Bayadera kali</i>	DD
		<i>Bayadera longicauda</i>	DD
		<i>Dysphaea ethela</i>	LC
		<i>Dysphaea gloriosa</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea cardinalis</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea dispar</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea fraseri</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea masoni</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea ochracea</i>	LC
		<i>Euphaea pseudodispar</i>	NE
		<i>Euphaea thosegharensis</i>	NE
		<i>Schmidtiphaea schmidi</i>	DD
		<i>Schmidtiphaea chittaranjani</i>	DD
	Family Lestidae	<i>Indolestes assamicus</i>	DD
		<i>Indolestes cyaneus</i>	LC
		<i>Indolestes gracilis</i>	LC
		<i>Indolestes indicus</i>	NT
		<i>Indolestes pulcherrimus</i>	DD
		<i>Lestes barbarus</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes concinnus</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes dorothea</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes elatus</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes garoensis</i>	DD
		<i>Lestes malabaricus</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes nigriceps</i>	DD
		<i>Lestes nodalis</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes patricia</i>	DD
		<i>Lestes praemorsus</i>	LC
		<i>Lestes viridulus</i>	LC
		<i>Orolestes durga</i>	DD
		<i>Orolestes selysi</i>	LC
		<i>Platylestes kirani</i>	NE
		<i>Platylestes platystylus</i>	LC
		<i>Sympecma paedisca</i>	LC
	Family Philogangidae	<i>Philoganga montana</i>	LC
		<i>Burmargiolestes laidlawi</i>	DD

	Family Platystictidae	<i>Drepanosticta annandalei</i>	DD
		<i>Drepanosticta carmichaeli</i>	LC
		<i>Drepanosticta polychromatica</i>	DD
		<i>Indosticta deccanensis</i>	V
		<i>Protosticta anamalaica</i>	NE
		<i>Protosticta armageddonia</i>	NE
		<i>Protosticta antelopoides</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta cyanofemora</i>	NE
		<i>Protosticta damacornu</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta davenporti</i>	LC
		<i>Protosticta francyi</i>	NE
		<i>Protosticta fraseri</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta graveleyi</i>	LC
		<i>Protosticta hearseyi</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta himalaica</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta monticola</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta mortoni</i>	NE
		<i>Protosticta myristicaensis</i>	CE
		<i>Protosticta ponmudiensis</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta rufostigma</i>	DD
		<i>Protosticta sanguinostigma</i>	V
		<i>Protosticta sholai</i>	NE
	Family Platycnemididae	<i>Caconeura gomphoides</i>	DD
		<i>Caconeura obscura</i>	DD
		<i>Caconeura ramburi</i>	DD
		<i>Caconeura risi</i>	DD
		<i>Caconeura t-coerulea</i>	DD
		<i>Calicnemia doonensis</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia erythromelas</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia eximia</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia imitans</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia miles</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia miniata</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia mortoni</i>	LC
		<i>Calicnemia mukherjeei</i>	DD
		<i>Calicnemia nipalica</i>	V
		<i>Calicnemia pulverulans</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia bimaculata</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia didyma</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia dorothea</i>	DD
		<i>Coeliccia fraseri</i>	V
		<i>Coeliccia loogali</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia prakritiae</i>	NE
		<i>Coeliccia renifera</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia rossi</i>	DD
		<i>Coeliccia rotundata</i>	DD
		<i>Coeliccia sarbottama</i>	DD
		<i>Coeliccia schmidti</i>	DD
		<i>Coeliccia svihleri</i>	LC
		<i>Coeliccia vacca</i>	DD
		<i>Copera marginipes</i>	LC
		<i>Copera vittata</i>	LC
		<i>Disparoneura apicalis</i>	V
		<i>Disparoneura quadrimaculata</i>	LC
		<i>Elatoneura atkinsoni</i>	NT
		<i>Elatoneura campioni</i>	DD
		<i>Elatoneura nigerrima</i>	DD
		<i>Elatoneura nihari</i>	DD
		<i>Elatoneura souteri</i>	DD
		<i>Elatoneura tetrica</i>	LC
		<i>Esme cyaneovittata</i>	DD
		<i>Esme longistyla</i>	LC
		<i>Esme mudiensis</i>	DD
		<i>Indocnemis orang</i>	LC
		<i>Melanoneura bilineata</i>	NT

		<i>Nososticta nancowra</i>	DD
		<i>Nososticta nicobarica</i>	DD
		<i>Onychargia atrocyana</i>	LC
		<i>Phylloneura westermanni</i>	NT
		<i>Platynemesis dealbata</i>	LC
		<i>Prodasinemesis autumnalis</i>	LC
		<i>Prodasinemesis odoneli</i>	DD
		<i>Prodasinemesis verticalis</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudocopera ciliata</i>	LC
		<i>Pseudocopera superplatypes</i>	DD
	Family Synlestidae	<i>Megalestes gyalsey</i>	DD
		<i>Megalestes irma</i>	DD
		<i>Megalestes kurahashii</i>	LC
		<i>Megalestes lieftincki</i>	DD
		<i>Megalestes major</i>	LC
		<i>Megalestes micans</i>	LC
Total	3	17	504

Least Concern (LC), Near Threatened (NT), Not Evaluated (NE), Endangered (E), Data Deficient (DD), Critically Endangered (CR),

Table 2. Comparison of Conservation Data of World and Indian Odonates.

Red List Categories	World Odonates	Indian Odonates	Indian Odonates %
EX	1	0	0
EW	0	0	0
CR	97	1	1.03
EN	310	3	0.96
VU	303	11	3.63
NT	236	13	5.5
LC	3447	281	8.15
DD	1829	164	0.08
NE	230	31	13.47
Total	6453	504	7.81

Graph 1. Relative Proportion of Listed Conservation Categories of Indian Odonates.

CONCLUSION

Maximum odonate species have conservation status of LC (n=281) and DD (N=164). List of Threatened species is negligible in India. Threat of extinction is almost null. However, yet many species listed under NE category create a gap in biodiversity data. Tremendous and excellent work on conservation of organism is done globally by IUCN and scientists. Despite of their pivotal role in aquatic ecosystem, odonates are ignored by most conservationists. Odonatologists must focus and assess NE odonate species. Although odonates have aesthetic value, they are biocontrol agent and bioindicators of aquatic ecosystem, they are ignored because they are not much economically important for humans. Further study on taxonomy and distribution of adult stages are relatively more done than larvae. There is most unexplored area in India, where no study is done on odonates. Many species need to be explored and discovered. More comprehensive work and data on odonates is required for assessing their true biodi

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